

A Mixed-Methods Framework for Mapping Graduate Research Contributions to the SDGs in Brazil

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Abstract

Mapping research contributions to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) remains a global challenge, particularly in the Global South, where language barriers, data gaps, and limited database coverage undermine comprehensive analysis. This article presents a mixed-methods framework developed by a national committee appointed by the Brazilian Agency for Support and Evaluation of Graduate Education (CAPES) to assess the contributions of Brazil's graduate research system to the 2030 Agenda. Drawing on the STRINGS methodology, the project developed bilingual descriptors and applied them to the Sucupira Platform, which records data from all accredited master's and doctoral programmes in the country. This approach enabled a large-scale and reproducible mapping of SDG-related theses and dissertations, complemented by three nationally defined goals—Ethnic-Racial Equality (SDG 18), Art, Culture, and Communication (SDG 19), and Rights of Indigenous Peoples and Traditional Communities (SDG 20). Benchmarking against OpenAlex provided an international reference point, while qualitative components—including disciplinary surveys, consultations with state departments of education, and programme-level case studies—added interpretive depth and contextual specificity. The Brazilian experience demonstrates how transparent, adaptable, and policy relevant methods can support more inclusive and responsible approaches to mapping research contributions to sustainable development.

Keywords: *Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), Research mapping, Graduate education, Global South research.*

Since the adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015, the integration of social, economic, and environmental dimensions has become a global priority, particularly in developing regions where data gaps and governance challenges persist (Caudill et al., 2024; Zhou & Moinuddin, 2023). Earlier frameworks, such as Agenda 21 and the Millennium Development Goals, laid the foundation for participatory and integrated approaches. However, the SDGs expanded both scope and complexity, underscoring inclusivity and interdependence (Krauss, Cisneros, & Requena-i-Mora, 2022; Litre et al., 2020).

In this context, research on technical methodologies to map scientific contributions to the SDG has emerged as a critical area of inquiry. These efforts reflect the global push to align science, technology, and innovation with the 2030 Agenda, with practical implications for policy, funding, and institutional strategies (Ciarli et al., 2022; Mishra et al., 2024; Raman et al., 2023). However, mapping aligned research in the Global South presents persistent challenges, including language barriers, reliance on local publication venues, limited coverage of outputs beyond journal articles, and disciplinary imbalances in international databases such as Web of Science and Scopus (Diop et al., 2022; Pateman, Tuhkanen, & Cinderby, 2021).

Brazil illustrates these challenges clearly. A significant share of its scholarly production is published in Portuguese and appears in local or regional journals not indexed internationally. Furthermore, the unbalancing of the disciplinary coverage in international databases is even more extreme for the country than for the global average (Brasil, 2021). As a result, approaches based solely on the mapping of articles in global databases risk producing biased or incomplete accounts of the country's contributions to the SDG.

In this context, the Brazilian Agency for Graduate Education Support and Evaluation (CAPES) coordinated a national effort to assess and present how research conducted in Brazilian universities and research institutions contributes to the advancement of the SDG. A dedicated committee was appointed for this task, comprising CAPES staff, representatives of all 50 disciplinary evaluation panels in the Brazilian National System of Graduate Education (SNPG), the National Forum of Pro-Rectors of Graduate Studies (FOPROP), and the National Association of Graduate Students (ANPG) (CAPES, 2024). The investigation materialised in the book "Impact of Brazilian graduate education on the 2030 Agenda", a contribution to the 30th Conference of the Parties (COP30) of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, held in the Brazilian Amazon in 2025 (Sampaio et al., 2025).

This article presents the more inclusive methodological approach developed by the committee to address the central challenge: how to comprehensively map the research contributions of a country to the SDGs when conventional bibliometric tools provide only a partial view. The strategy extended beyond international journal articles to include graduate-level theses and dissertations systematically collected through national research information systems. It builds on, but also moves beyond, international initiatives such as the Aurora SDG Classifier, Elsevier’s SDG mapping in Scopus, and the STRINGS project.

To complement this quantitative mapping, the committee incorporated qualitative inputs. A national survey of evaluation panel coordinators provided disciplinary perspectives on SDG-related research, while consultations with state departments of education examined how sustainability themes and SDGs are interpreted in basic and secondary education policies throughout Brazil. Together with case studies submitted by graduate programme directors, these components offered complementary vantage points—connecting research production, educational policy, and local practice. By documenting this process, the article presents the integrative approach of the committee, highlights its potential and limitations, and contributes to broader debates on the design of inclusive and policy-relevant methodologies to map the contributions of research to sustainable development.

Traditional methods for mapping SDG research and their limitations

Several initiatives have sought to identify and classify research outputs in relation to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. These methods are designed to support evidence-based policy, evaluation and strategic planning, but differ significantly in terms of transparency, coverage, and adaptability. Among the most widely used are the STRINGS project (Confraria et al., 2024), the Aurora Universities Network queries (Vanderfeesten, Otten, & Spielberg, 2020), and Elsevier’s SDG classification system (Elsevier & Group, 2020).

The STRINGS project (Steering Research and Innovation for Global Goals) is notable for its open and reproducible design. By publishing search strings for each of the SDGs and making them adaptable across bibliometric databases such as Web of Science and Scopus, STRINGS enables researchers to translate and refine queries in diverse contexts. This openness contrasts with Elsevier’s proprietary classification algorithm, which uses a combination of curated keyword sets and machine learning within Scopus and SciVal. Although Elsevier’s approach scales automatically in large

datasets, its reliance on a commercial platform and limited disclosure of the methods restrict reproducibility (Kashnitsky et al., 2024; Raman et al., 2023). The Aurora University Network has focused on institutional alignment with the SDG, improving keyword-based searches, and testing multilingual extensions. However, it remains dependent on the coverage and biases of international databases. Other initiatives, such as SIRIS, SDSN and OSDG tools, also contribute alternative labelling systems with varying levels of transparency (Pukelis et al., 2022; Vanderfeesten, Spielberg, & Gunes, 2020).

Comparative studies show that these systems rarely converge on the same set of publications. The overlap between the STRINGS, Aurora, Elsevier, and SIRIS outputs is consistently low, with differences driven by query construction, keyword selection, and database coverage (Armitage, Lorenz, & Mikki, 2020; Li, Zhao, & Shen, 2024; Purnell, 2022). Such inconsistencies limit their usefulness for benchmarking or national policy applications (Wulff, Meier, & Mata, 2024). Even when more advanced methods such as clustering of citations or ensemble classifiers are applied, the results remain sensitive to the choice of training data, algorithms, and thresholds (Ingram, Banerjee, & Fox, 2024; Pal & Mukhopadhyay, 2024; Yin et al., 2023). Proprietary systems exacerbate the problem by withholding methodological details, further restricting independent validation (Kashnitsky et al., 2024; Raman et al., 2023).

Although machine learning and ensemble models offer promise, they also introduce practical obstacles. Transformer-based models, such as BERT or RoBERTa, which are increasingly used for the classification of SDG (Angin et al., 2022; Barros et al., 2024), require large, expert-labelled datasets and substantial computational resources. For national initiatives with constrained timelines or the need for reproducibility between multiple institutions, such approaches can be challenging to implement. Moreover, these tools remain tied to the same indexed sources that under-represent research outputs from non-English languages, local journals, and formats such as theses and dissertations.

In summary, traditional methods for mapping SDG research have generated valuable tools and insights but remain limited by coverage, language, disciplinary, and transparency biases. These shortcomings are especially pronounced in contexts such as Brazil and the broader Global South, where the national research system is characterised by linguistic diversity and a firm reliance on locally orientated publication venues. Addressing these gaps required adapting existing methodologies to Brazilian realities, a process that began with systematic testing of available approaches. The following section outlines this quantitative start, focusing on the

evaluation of different query-based methods and the choice of STRINGS as the basis for Brazil's mapping strategy.

The Brazilian approach: a quantitative start

The starting point for the Brazilian mapping effort was a systematic assessment of alternative methodologies to identify research related to the SDG. Algorithms were developed to operationalise both the Aurora Universities Network queries and the STRINGS project methodology. This comparative exercise revealed important differences. Aurora queries produced a larger volume of results overall. However, manual inspection revealed that a significant proportion of these outputs represented false positives or were only tangentially related to the SDG. STRINGS, by contrast, retrieved a smaller number of works, but with greater specificity. Given the project's objective of establishing a credible and representative baseline to evaluate the contributions of graduate research to the 2030 Agenda, precision was prioritised. STRINGS was therefore selected as the core algorithm for the national mapping.

The choice of STRINGS was also justified by its openness, methodological clarity, and replicability. As a query-based approach, STRINGS descriptors are transparent and can be adapted to different contexts. This made it possible to build algorithms in SQL that are both auditable and easily replicable across different datasets, which is particularly important, as applying these queries to international bibliometric databases would have reproduced the limitations already mentioned, particularly in relation to coverage, language, and document type. To overcome these constraints, the project relied on one of the most robust national Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) in Brazil, known as the Sucupira Platform.

CAPES-managed as part of the country's mandatory evaluation system, Sucupira serves as a central data repository for all accredited graduate programmes in Brazil (PPG). Collect data on faculty, students, courses, projects, research outputs, and other relevant information. Since evaluation is a high-stakes process in the country, the coverage and quality of available information is significantly high (Brasil & Trevisol, 2025). To map the contributions of Brazilian graduate education to Agenda 2030, approximately 700,000 theses and dissertations submitted between 2013 and 2022 by more than 4,500 graduate programmes were obtained from Sucupira and compiled into a relational database. These relate to virtually every master's or PhD defence in the country during the period, and the available metadata included titles, abstracts, and keywords in Portuguese, as well as, when available, English.

Although a substantial proportion of the records contained English abstracts and keywords, a significant share of the corpus was available only in Portuguese. It was therefore necessary to adapt the STRINGS descriptors through systematic translation and localisation. All descriptors were translated into Brazilian Portuguese and refined to capture local terminology, spelling conventions, and disciplinary usage. The translation process was also based on a robust set of descriptors for SDG-related research developed in Brazil (Junior et al., 2023), ensuring alignment with national policy documents and thematic vocabularies.

The final approach applied bilingual queries in parallel, matching both Portuguese and English descriptors to titles, abstracts, and keywords. The algorithms were implemented in SQL, using the Google Cloud platform for execution, which enabled efficient large-scale processing of the corpus while ensuring replicability and transparency (Brasil, 2025).

The use of Sucupira and the decision to go beyond articles not only addressed the structural under-representation of Global South research in international databases but also allowed for a more inclusive portrait of research activity, particularly in fields such as education, public health and social sciences. Since graduate education accounts for most of Brazil’s scientific output and Sucupira provides a uniquely comprehensive and standardised dataset that includes non-indexed research (Brasil, 2023), the Brazilian initiative was able to build a more complete and contextually grounded mapping of SDG-related research that combined the strengths of a robust national CRIS with an open methodological framework.

Complementary goals in the Brazilian context

An additional benefit of adapting STRINGS to prepare the mapping algorithm of the project was that the study was not limited to the 17 SDGs of the United Nations. As part of the book “Impact of Brazilian Graduate Education on the 2030 Agenda”, the mapping also covered three complementary goals proposed in the Brazilian context. These goals, described in the following along with their relevance, were developed through a consultative process and aimed to capture the dimensions of sustainable development that are critical to the social fabric of Brazil and are under-represented in the international framework of the SDGs (Cabral & Galvão, 2025).

SDG 18: Ethnic–Racial Equality was formally launched by the Brazilian government in November 2024 during the G20 Social, with ten goals focused on eliminating structural racism and guaranteeing rights in domains such as justice, health, hous-

ing, education, memory, and reparation. Its inclusion responds to Brazil's history of racial inequality and the need to integrate anti-racist policies into the wider sustainability agenda. Mapping research output related to SDG 18 is crucial to assessing how academic knowledge supports policy measures aimed at confronting systemic racial disparities.

SDG 19: Art, Culture, and Communication emerged from longstanding debates, led by UNESCO and national cultural policy forums, on the transversal role of culture in sustainable development. Although culture is acknowledged as a cross-cutting factor influencing all SDGs, it does not have a dedicated goal in the UN framework. In Brazil, the Ministry of Culture has advanced this agenda by consolidating cultural sustainability as both an end in itself and a means to achieve other goals. Incorporating SDG 19 into the mapping exercise allows recognition of the substantial body of graduate research in the arts, culture, and communication that would otherwise be invisible in SDG-focused analyses.

SDG 20: Rights of Indigenous Peoples and Traditional Communities is grounded in international commitments, such as the ILO Convention 169 and the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, but is contextualised to address Brazil's national challenges, including territorial rights, cultural preservation, and recognition of traditional knowledge. Brazil hosts one of the largest and most diverse populations of indigenous and traditional communities in the world, whose contributions to biodiversity conservation and sustainability are increasingly recognised (Caudill et al., 2024; Krauss, Cisneros, & Requena-i-Mora, 2022). Mapping graduate research output related to SDG 20 provides a way to assess how the academic system contributes to safeguarding these rights and valorising Indigenous knowledge within the national development agenda.

These three goals were defined using the same transparent query-based logic as the STRINGS methodology, drawing also from national policy documents, expert consultations, and thematic vocabularies (Junior et al., 2023). This ensured methodological consistency while aligning the mapping framework with Brazil's social realities and strengthening Brazil's commitment to a decolonial and plural understanding of sustainable development. It also addresses calls within the literature to move beyond a one-size-fits-all framework by recognising diverse pathways to sustainability and the importance of epistemic diversity (Ràfols et al., 2021).

Benchmarking against international data

Although Sucupira offers a uniquely comprehensive and linguistically inclusive view of Brazilian graduate research, it was essential to situate these findings within the broader global research landscape. To achieve this, the project incorporated a benchmarking component using OpenAlex, an open and integrative bibliographic database developed as a public alternative to proprietary platforms.

OpenAlex was chosen for its comprehensive coverage across multiple data sources, including open-access repositories and doctoral theses. Unlike databases with narrower coverage, OpenAlex provides a more suitable basis for comparative analysis. The infrastructure developed by InSySPo, a research project at the University of Campinas (UNICAMP), in Brazil, supported the processing and analysis of OpenAlex data using the adapted STRINGS methodology applied to Sucupira, ensuring methodological consistency.

Benchmarking served three main purposes. First, it enabled comparative validation. By applying identical query sets to both datasets, the team was able to evaluate how Brazilian research appears in international sources and to identify discrepancies arising from differences in document types, language coverage, and indexing scope. Second, it facilitated international contextualisation. The exercise placed Brazil's research output in relation to global trends in the 17 SDGs, revealing areas of thematic convergence and divergence. Third, the analysis assessed the applicability of Brazil's complementary goals: SDG 18 (Ethnic–Racial Equality), 19 (Art, Culture, and Communication), and 20 (Rights of Indigenous Peoples and Traditional Communities) beyond the national context. By extending these descriptors to OpenAlex, the team explored how topics related to race, culture, and Indigenous rights are represented globally. The findings highlighted both areas of alignment, such as indigenous knowledge and biodiversity conservation, and areas where Brazil's contributions remain uniquely positioned or under-represented in the international literature.

The benchmarking process underscored the value of combining CRIS data with open international databases. While Sucupira ensured comprehensiveness and coverage of non-indexed, locally produced outputs, OpenAlex offered comparative reach and an external perspective. Together, they allowed a more multidimensional understanding of Brazil's contributions to the SDGs, bridging global agendas and locally defined priorities.

Results of the quantitative mapping

The application of the adapted STRINGS methodology to the Sucupira data set enabled a systematic analysis of graduate-level research outputs in Brazil in relation to the 2030 Agenda. However, this article does not aim to present a comprehensive account of these results, as Sampaio et al. (2025) offers, in its many chapters, in-depth analyses of the large-scale mapping effort through multiple lenses: temporal, thematic, disciplinary, and geographic. Rather than detailing those results, this article focuses on the methodological approach that enabled such analyses. However, a brief look at some of the results from the quantitative analyses reveals the value in the approach taken.

To illustrate this point, Figure 1 presents the percentage distribution of theses and dissertations from Brazilian graduate programmes across the Sustainable Development Goals between 2013 and 2022. The chart uses fractional counting, ensuring that theses or dissertations related to more than one SDG are proportionally allocated rather than double-counted. This approach provides a more accurate representation of contributions across goals. The complementary SDGs (18–20) are also included.

Figure 1: Percentage of theses and dissertations from Brazilian graduate programmes related to Sustainable Development Goals

The distribution patterns revealed are particularly notable. One of the clearest trends is the decrease in the proportion of works not related to any SDG. At the

beginning of the period, nearly 50% of theses and dissertations did not align with any of the goals; however, by 2022, this share had fallen to less than 35%. This decrease, represented by the dark grey bar at the bottom of the figure, suggests that graduate research is progressively becoming more engaged with sustainability-related topics.

Among the SDGs, some stand out as receiving greater attention: SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), SDG 4 (Quality Education), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), and SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities). At the same time, relative growth across the SDGs is fairly even, indicating that attention has expanded broadly rather than being disproportionately directed to some goals.

However, the most significant strength of the analysis presented in Figure 1 lies in its completeness. The data set includes the near totality of graduate theses and dissertations produced in Brazil during the period, without language restrictions, geographical exclusions, or dependence on international indexing practices. This ensures that the analysis captures the true scope of graduate research in the country and avoids biases commonly found in bibliometric studies based on selective databases.

Furthermore, an additional advantage of mapping theses and dissertations from the Sucupira Platform is the breadth of information available, which provides the ability to track contributions at multiple levels, including individual graduate students, supervisors, research projects, graduate programmes, institutions, and states. The extensive coverage of micro-level data enables policymakers and researchers to conduct diverse analyses of interest. For example, Figure 1 showed Health and Well-being (SDG 3) as the most prominent SDG in Brazilian graduate research. To expand on this, Figure 2A presents the average number of theses and dissertations per graduate programme related to SDG 3 in all fields. The map uses the average number of products to account for the asymmetric distribution of PPG in the country, which would otherwise skew the concentration towards the southeast region.

Figure 2: Average number of theses and dissertations per programme related to SDG 3 (Health and Well-Being) in (a) all programmes; (b) life sciences; (c) social sciences and humanities; and (d) SDG 19 (Indigenous peoples and traditional communities).

Figure 2a reveals that the state of São Paulo has the highest overall contribution, with more than 40,000 theses and dissertations produced by 947 PPG in 2013–2022. At the other end of the spectrum, Rondônia registers an average of only 16 works per programme, representing roughly 300 theses and dissertations distributed among 18 programmes.

Figures 2b and 2c offer a disciplinary perspective on SDG 3. Figure 2b focuses on graduate programmes in the life sciences, where the average number of theses and dissertations per programme increases considerably. Rio de Janeiro emerges as the city with the highest concentration, producing nearly 13,000 works in 143 programmes. Figure 2c highlights contributions from the social sciences and humanities, where output levels are lower, as expected. In Espírito Santo, the state with the highest average, 741 theses and dissertations related to SDG 3 were produced by 29

programmes, resulting in an average of approximately 25 works per PPG. Finally, Figure 2d shifts the attention to the complementary SDG 19, a nationally defined goal that addresses the rights of indigenous peoples and traditional communities. The distribution of research on this topic reflects strong regional patterns. States in the northern region, particularly those connected to the Amazon, show a higher concentration of contributions. This alignment between research focus and regional priorities underscores the value of the mapping exercise in revealing not only disciplinary and institutional patterns, but also how local contexts shape the orientation of graduate research.

Integrating a qualitative layer

Quantitative mapping methods based on algorithmic and bibliometric tools provide important insights into the scale and distribution of SDG-related research. However, they are limited in their ability to capture social complexity, local engagement, and the feedback mechanisms linking research, education, and policy. As a result, these methods risk reinforcing structural exclusions and epistemic hierarchies, particularly in contexts where knowledge production takes diverse and often non-standard forms (Mbah & East, 2022). Therefore, recent literature has called for the integration of epistemic diversity and the recognition of local and Indigenous knowledge systems, as well as the inclusion of evidence from educational policy practice, to support more just and context-sensitive sustainability pathways (Caudill et al., 2024; Ghosh et al., 2021; Krauss, Cisneros, & Requena-i-Mora, 2022).

In line with these perspectives, the mapping framework developed for the book *Impact of Brazilian Graduate Education on the 2030 Agenda* included a qualitative layer designed to complement the large-scale analysis of theses and dissertations. The purpose of the project was to add disciplinary depth, policy relevance, and contextual specificity to the mapping process, giving visibility to research and educational practices that are not easily captured by bibliometric indicators.

Previous studies have demonstrated the value of qualitative approaches — including participatory mapping, narrative accounts, and case studies — to uncover situated forms of engagement and knowledge production that remain invisible in metadata-driven assessments (Ledezma, 2023; Oliveira et al., 2024). Thus, three interrelated components were implemented: a survey of disciplinary coordinators, a nationwide call for case studies from graduate programmes, and consultations with state departments of education. The first component provided an expert disciplinary interpretation of SDGs-related research; the second documented practical examples

of research and outreach connecting universities to local sustainability challenges; and the third established a bridge between graduate education and basic education by identifying state-level initiatives that integrate Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) into curriculum and teacher training. Together, these components enriched the interpretive richness of the mapping, highlighted limitations in the coverage and granularity of bibliometric data, and illuminated practices of research engagement that are central to sustainable development but often excluded from publication-based assessments.

Survey of evaluation area coordinators

Brazil's graduate education system is structured into 50 evaluation areas, each coordinated by a panel of scholars responsible for assessing academic programmes in their field. These panels, under the national evaluation system administered by CAPES, bring deep expertise in disciplinary research practices, epistemologies, and emerging thematic priorities.

A structured survey was sent to all 50 area coordinators with three guiding questions.

- How does research in your field relate to the 17 UN SDGs and the three complementary goals defined in the Brazilian context (SDG 18–20)?
- What research projects, training initiatives, outreach efforts, or partnerships exemplify this engagement?
- What opportunities and challenges do you have to advance the work related to the SDG within your discipline?

Responses were received from all 50 panels, producing a comprehensive cross-section of disciplinary perspectives. The results revealed substantial heterogeneity in the way the SDGs are interpreted and operationalised across fields. In health-related areas, such as Medicine and Nursing, emphasis is placed on SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), often linked to research on public health systems, epidemiology, and medical education. In Environmental and Agricultural Sciences, SDG 14 (Life Below Water) and SDG 15 (Life on Land) were central, particularly in association with biodiversity studies, agroecology and ecosystem restoration.

The humanities and Social Sciences panels frequently referenced SDG 4 (Quality Education), SDG 5 (Gender Equality) and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), drawing connexions to anti-racist education, indigenous knowledge, cultural heritage, and

community research. Legal studies, anthropology, and related fields are critically involved in SDG 20, focusing on territorial rights, intercultural dialogue, and the epistemological plurality required to support traditional communities.

In addition to identifying thematic alignments, many coordinators highlighted institutional and epistemic barriers to further integrating the SDGs into graduate research, including disciplinary silos, funding constraints, and the undervaluation of applied or locally rooted scholarship. These reflections served as a disciplinary map of how Brazilian graduate education interprets and contributes to the 2030 Agenda, complementing algorithmic mapping with situated expertise.

Consultations with state departments of education

A further layer of qualitative evidence involved consultations with state departments of education to explore how the Sustainable Development Goals are being operationalised in basic and secondary education and how graduate programmes can contribute to this process. Conducted through structured questionnaires distributed to all 27 Brazilian federative units in late 2024, this consultation aimed to identify local initiatives, partnerships, and challenges in linking education policy, teacher training, and sustainability-orientated curricula. 22 states responded, revealing that at least three-quarters of the Brazilian states had established partnerships with public universities and federal institutes to implement projects aligned with the SDGs, particularly those involving environmental education, teacher capacity building, and educational innovation (Gonçalves et al., 2025).

The inclusion of this component provided an institutional bridge between graduate education and public education policy, showing how research carried out in master's and doctoral programmes is translated into pedagogical practices, teaching materials, and capacity building activities for teachers. It also illuminated the reciprocal side of this relationship, how the priorities emerging from basic education, such as the implementation of a national common curricular base and the integration of transversal sustainability themes, stimulate new research agendas within universities. By linking graduate research with the public-school system, this consultation underscored the systemic nature of sustainability education and demonstrated the potential for mutual learning between academic and policy communities.

The triangulation of disciplinary expertise, programme level practices, and state policy perspectives offered a richer interpretive framework for the data obtained through the national mapping. It enriched the understanding of how graduate research contributes not only to scientific knowledge but also to educational trans-

formation, demonstrating that sustainable development depends on coherent and continuous action across the entire educational spectrum, from early schooling to advanced research training.

Call for case studies from graduate programmes

To complement the system-level disciplinary perspective with more grounded accounts of practice, a nationwide call for case studies was issued to all accredited graduate programmes in Brazil. Programme directors were invited to submit examples of research, teaching, or outreach activities that contributed to one or more of the SDGs. The submission process was deliberately open, allowing for diverse formats and thematic orientations, including completed work, ongoing projects, and long-term institutional initiatives (Sampaio et al., 2025).

The response was substantial: 1,950 case studies were submitted by 1,058 graduate programmes, covering every major disciplinary field and all five Brazilian regions. This corpus revealed the breadth of ways in which graduate programmes engage with sustainability challenges in context-specific and often innovative ways. The received cases, which illustrate how Brazilian Postgraduate studies contribute to the SDGs, were mainly selected by the 50 area coordinators. The selected cases by area were grouped by knowledge major areas, grouped into three schools: Life Sciences, Humanities, and Exact, Technological, and Multidisciplinary Sciences, totalling 36 selected cases. Each case, in each broad area, aimed to meet four different scopes: i) meet the largest possible number of SDGs, ii) meet the demands of the Amazon, with a leading role for Amazon Graduate Programmes, iii) meet the needs imposed by Climate Change (leading role in SDG 13), iv) meet the Adjacent SDGs: which meets an eminently Brazilian initiative related to SDG 18 – Ethnic-Racial Equality, SDG 19 – Art, Culture and Communication and SDG 20 – Indigenous Peoples and Traditional Communities. The criteria used in selecting the cases were: meeting at least one SDG from each of these three dimensions, social, environmental, and economic, in addition to the three adjacent SDGs, in correlation with Teaching and/or Research/Innovation and/or activities with the community, in addition to the robustness of the text and level of maturity of the initiative.

Examples include

- Engineering programmes that developed low-cost water purification systems for underserved rural communities.

- Social science projects using participatory methods to address food insecurity in urban peripheries.
- Public health initiatives focused on maternal and child health, implemented in partnership with local clinics and NGOs.
- Educational interventions designed to promote environmental literacy among primary and secondary school students in the Amazon region.
- Legal clinics working with Indigenous communities to advance territorial claims and cultural rights are aligned with SDG 20.
- The biotechnological potential for agricultural sustainability, with an impact on productivity and environmental responsibility, is explored in a network project involving several states of the country. This project has led to the development of new products and processes that have reached the market.

These case studies, a selection of which were published in the final book, illustrated the multiple and often non-linear pathways through which graduate research contributes to sustainable development. They also documented forms of impact — such as capacity building, local empowerment, and knowledge co-production — that are not easily captured by conventional bibliometric indicators. By opening space for institutional voices and grassroots perspectives, the case study component reinforced the project’s commitment to methodological pluralism and inclusion in sustainability assessment.

Conclusions

Mapping research contributions to the Sustainable Development Goals requires more than technical precision; it requires methodological pluralism, contextual sensitivity, and institutional inclusivity. This article has presented an integrative framework developed in Brazil to assess the contributions of graduate research to the 2030 Agenda. Grounded in both quantitative and qualitative components, the approach goes beyond conventional bibliometric tools by incorporating national CRIS data, bilingual query design, expert consultation, educational policy engagement, and programme-level case studies. The result is a more comprehensive and situated account of how graduate education contributes to sustainable development.

By adapting and extending the STRINGS methodology to a national corpus of nearly 700,000 theses and dissertations, the project addressed long-standing gaps in

international SDG mapping practices, particularly those related to language coverage, document types, and disciplinary imbalances. The inclusion of three complementary goals — Ethnic–Racial Equality, Art, Culture and Communication, and Indigenous and Traditional Rights — further grounded the exercise in the social and epistemic realities of Brazil. Benchmarking against OpenAlex demonstrated the value of combining national and international datasets, while highlighting the continued under-representation of research from the Global South on global platforms.

Equally important was the expansion of the qualitative layer, now encompassing disciplinary, institutional, and policy perspectives. The evaluation panel survey revealed how sustainability is interpreted within different academic fields; case studies from graduate programmes illustrated concrete pathways of societal impact; and consultations with state departments of education illuminated how the results of graduate research inform and support the implementation of sustainability and environmental education across the public-school system. Together, these perspectives highlight the role of graduate education not only as a site of knowledge production, but also as a catalyst for transforming educational practices, teacher training, and policy innovation at multiple levels.

As countries strive to align science and education with global sustainability goals, the Brazilian experience provides a replicable yet adaptable model. It underscores the need for transparent and reproducible methodologies that recognise local priorities and value diverse forms of knowledge. Future work can build on this foundation by integrating new data sources, expanding comparative analyses, and improving tools for continuous monitoring and policy learning. By doing so, national research systems can contribute more effectively—and more equitably—to the global pursuit of sustainable development.

Conflicts of interest:

The authors declare they don't have any commercial or associative interest that represents a conflict of interest in relation to the manuscript.

Data availability statement:

The data and algorithms that support the findings of this study are openly available in OSF at <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/9GYVB>. Additional data are publicly available at <https://dadosabertos.capes.gov.br> and <https://openalex.org>.

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